

Visualization of Early Islamicate Scholars' Network

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Because of the fragmented material found in biographies, early Islamic texts are especially valuable for comprehending the intellectual history of the time and have a structure that makes historical networks possible. Although there are few manuscripts from the first three hijrī centuries to the present (Schoeler, 2022, 81), understanding the flow of knowledge during these centuries is made easier by the chains of transmission (isnāds) found in later circulating literature (Muther et.al., 2023, 2; Saraçoğlu, 2023, 20-24). Texts that have been circulating since the third hijrī century contain chains of transmission that date back to the time of the Prophet Muhammad. These chains involve individuals passing along knowledge fragments (narratives). Names and phrases that signify knowledge sharing between these people make up isnads. By digitizing names and their relationships and creating a network structure, the participants in the era's intellectual history become visible. Isnads have great historical significance as a result.

Although several studies (Kızıl, 2013; Yılmaz, 2020; Pavlovitch, 2020; Saraçoğlu, 2023) have graphically shown the relationships between scholars based on isnāds. However, it is very impossible to manually consolidate a book's all isnads. Network analysis is therefore very useful for social scientists. Historical ties can be reinterpreted using social network analysis of isnads, and main actors can be found using centrality measures. The visualization options that network analysis provides for isnad representation are another important contribution.

In this article, we discuss converting isnāds text to data, and visualization of the transmission networks in the framework of Ibn Sa'd's *Kitābu't-Ṭabaqātī'l-Kabīr*. The first two volumes of that book are among the earliest sīra texts of Islamic historiography. 2,258 isnad chains of nearly 2,000 rāwis/transmitters in these volumes (Saraçoğlu, 2023, 112) were regarded as a social network to explore the main sources of that book. In this network, the rāwis in the isnads are actors, and their connections formed by their narrative relationship through akhbarana, haddathana, 'an etc. are the ties. It is possible to develop a structured data set with the rāwies names and their relations in an isnād chain as below.

أَخْبَرَنَا مُحَمَّدُ بْنُ عُمَرَ، أَخْبَرَنَا إِبْرَاهِيمُ بْنُ إِسْمَاعِيلَ بْنِ أَبِي حَبِيبَةَ، عَنْ دَاوُدَ بْنِ

الْحَصِينِ، عَنْ عِكْرِمَةَ، عَنِ ابْنِ عَبَّاسٍ، قَالَ... (متن)

Muhammad b. 'Omar said to us, Ibrāhīm b. Ismāīl b. Abū Habība said to him, and he [heard] from Dāvūd b. al-Husayn, from Ikrima from Ibn 'Abbās, and he said.... (text)

'Ibn Abbās	Ikrima	Dāvūd b. al-Husayn	Ibrāhīm b. Ismāīl b. Abū Habība	Muhammad b. 'Omar	Ibn Sa'd
d. 68/687-88	d. 105/723	d. 135/753	d. 165/782	d. 207/823	d. 230/845

